

Project CHANGES - Spoke 5

D1.2 - Report on the validation of the new diagnostics with pilot cases

Deliverable information

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Executive Summary

This report presents the development of a robotic scanning system designed for non-invasive diagnostics using X-ray fluorescence (XRF) scanning. Special attention is paid to robotic path planning (or robotic arm path planning), 3D spatial mapping, and user-guided interaction. The report aligns with the objectives and technical guidelines of WP1 of the CHANGES project, as outlined in Deliverable D1.1 - Technical Report on Multimodal Diagnostic Design. WP1 aims to develop advanced and sustainable diagnostic methodologies for cultural heritage science by integrating multimodal instrumentation and automation in the analysis of material composition, stratigraphy, and degradation phenomena on artifacts and cultural heritage.

In this context, the developed robotic system complements the objectives of WP1 by enabling precise and repeatable scanner positioning in complex three-dimensional geometries, such as those found in artworks and artifacts, typically characterized by irregular concavities, convexities, and protuberances, as well as shape, surface, and material deformations. The system's key components (motion planning with collision detection, surface-constrained path generation on spherical geometries, and a customizable user interface for scanning configuration) create a dynamic framework for the implementation of diagnostic tools such as XRF, but also – potentially – hyperspectral and multispectral imaging, FTIR, etc.

The report presented here highlights the contribution of the robotic arm to improving the accuracy, adaptability and automation of cultural heritage diagnostics. Furthermore, the continued development of the graphical interface for scan planning and rescan targeting aligns with WP1's emphasis on usability and field implementation, offering intuitive control over diagnostic procedures for non-expert users in museum or conservation environments.

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1. Introduction

The present work documents the development and ongoing experimentation within the *Robotic Arm Scan* project, aiming to establish a flexible, modular scanning pipeline for cultural heritage applications. The system is being developed using the UR10e robotic arm in conjunction with the MoveIt motion planning framework. Significant progress has been achieved on the software side. Core functionalities - including simulated planning [1, 4], collision detection [1], inverse kinematics (IK) [2, 3], and a preliminary user interface (UI) - have been implemented and tested.

This document summarises the activities carried out to date, identifies technical gaps, and presents the next steps for achieving complete system integration, including communication protocols with the scanner and enhanced path planning strategies. Embedded video material accompanies the report to illustrate the current state of development and challenges encountered.

2. Pilot Case

A pilot study was conducted to enable the safe development of a robotic scanning system for artworks. Given their significant cultural and historical value, artworks must be handled with the utmost care and respect. To facilitate automated scanning, a high-precision robotic arm is employed. However, any type of failure—such as configuration errors, software bugs, or parameter misinterpretation—could result in irreversible damage to the artifact. To mitigate these risks, the project incorporates multiple layers of safety measures. The first measure involves defining a “safe zone” around the artwork, guiding the robotic arm’s permissible workspace. A spherical shape was selected to represent this zone due to its favourable geometric properties, including simplified collision detection and user-friendly configuration requiring only a single parameter. Future phases of the project will introduce additional safeguards to further enhance the reliability and safety of the scanning process.

3. Results

3.1 Collision Object Integration

Initial work involved the integration of virtual collision objects into the MoveIt environment to simulate a scanning context. Two objects were introduced: a static table, with hardcoded dimensions and position, and a user-defined spherical volume representing the object to be scanned. These elements guide the planner in generating valid, collision-free trajectories by enforcing spatial constraints. Demonstrations show how removing the table results in unintended collisions with the sphere, highlighting the importance of contextual geometry during planning ([Video 1](#), [Video 2](#)).

3.2 Path Planning and Inverse Kinematics

Subsequent efforts focused on defining scanning poses on the sphere surface. A configurable algorithm was implemented to generate poses around the object at a given height, with the robot's end-effector oriented towards the sphere's centre [4]. This method supports arbitrary numbers of scanning points and proved effective in most scenarios. Nonetheless, some unexpected path behaviours were observed—likely due to Cartesian goal specification or planner local minima. Multiple planners in MoveIt were tested, but none resolved the issue entirely.

To improve trajectory reliability, the TRAC-IK inverse kinematics solver [5] was integrated, significantly enhancing planning robustness in Cartesian space. The current algorithm successfully computes and executes up to 20 scanning poses, although minor execution failures remain ([Video](#)). Further improvements are expected by combining joint-space control with Screw Theory, which may offer more optimised scanning paths.

3.3 Interface and Visual Tools

A prototype graphical user interface (GUI) was developed using Iridescence, aimed at improving user interaction beyond the constraints of RVIZ. While RVIZ excels at visualising ROS messages for debugging, it is not optimal for end-user configuration. The new GUI enables manipulation of the scanning sphere in 3D space and selection of surface points. It also offers preliminary support for mesh visualisation and rescan selection [6].

Though the current integration is limited, ongoing development aims to streamline real-time interaction ([Demo](#)).

4. Methodology

4.1 Simulation and Software Infrastructure

A simulation environment was established using Docker and ROS packages to manage the UR10e robotic arm. A GitHub repository was created to maintain the workspace ([Repo 1](#), [Repo 2](#)). Motion control is achieved through a custom Movelt interface that allows for manual or automated joint command execution [7].

A sphere was initially added to Movelt as a "no-go" zone to support obstacle-aware motion planning. The sphere's location and radius are user-defined, enabling flexible adaptation to different scanning scenarios. Pose generation is handled through a custom planner, and inverse kinematics computations are carried out using TRAC-IK.

4.2 Path Optimisation and Future Work

Despite positive initial results, some issues with trajectory optimisation persist, particularly in transitions between poses. The investigation into advanced planning strategies is ongoing. Potential solutions include implementing a custom planner in OMPL [8] to constrain movements on the sphere surface or deriving an analytical IK model to maintain end-effector orientation [3].

Additionally, the team is exploring the use of real-time forward kinematics (FK) to track the scanner's position within the robot's reference frame. While the integration with the 3D scanner hardware is pending, the project has already acquired the necessary HW/SW components for UR10 communication, which is expected to simplify the final stages of integration.

4. Conclusions

Significant advancements have been made in the development of a robotic scanning pipeline using MoveIt and the UR10e platform. Core functionalities such as collision object modelling, pose generation, and inverse kinematics are in place and have been validated through simulations and video demonstrations. The integration of TRAC-IK has improved the stability of planned motions, and further refinement is expected through custom planning strategies and FK-based feedback.

A user interface prototype now enables intuitive configuration of scanning parameters, a crucial step toward operational usability. However, full integration with the scanner hardware remains to be completed. The next phases will focus on hardware communication protocols, FK node implementation, GUI refinement, and trajectory optimisation using mathematical planning techniques.

Feedback from colleagues and stakeholders is welcomed, as the project transitions from foundational development to full system integration and testing.

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